

Montoro, P. R., Villalba-García, C., Luna, D., & Hinojosa, J. A. (2017). Common region wins the competition between extrinsic grouping cues: Evidence from a task without explicit attention to grouping. *Psychonomic Bulletin and Review*, 24(6), 1856-1861. <https://doi.org/10.3758/S13423-017-1254-3>

1 **Common region wins the competition between extrinsic grouping cues: evidence**
2 **from a task without explicit attention to grouping**

3

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17

18 **Running head:** Competition between extrinsic grouping cues

19 **Abstract**

20 The competition between perceptual grouping factors is a relatively ignored topic,
21 especially in the case of extrinsic grouping cues (e.g., *common region* or
22 *connectedness*). Recent studies have examined the integration of extrinsic cues using
23 tasks that induce selective attention to groups based on different grouping cues.
24 However, this procedure could generate alternative strategies for task performance,
25 which are non-related to the perceptual grouping operations. In the current work, we
26 used an indirect task, i.e. *repetition discrimination task*, without explicit attention to
27 grouping cues to further examine the rules that govern dominance between competing
28 extrinsic grouping factors. This procedure allowed us to obtain an unbiased measure of
29 the competition between common region and connectedness cues acting within the same
30 display. The results corroborate previous data showing that grouping by common region
31 dominated the perceived organization of the display, even though the phenomenological
32 strength of the grouping cues was equated for each participant by means of a
33 preliminary scaling task. Our results highlight the relevance of using indirect tasks as an
34 essential tool for the systematic study of the integration between extrinsic grouping
35 cues.

36

37 **Keywords:** Gestalt; perceptual grouping; extrinsic principles; grouping by common
38 region; grouping by connectedness.

39

40 **Introduction**

41 Perceptual organization is the architecture studio of vision, which is in charge of
42 fitting together the pieces of the retinal mosaic to build a tidy visual experience. The
43 seminal work of Wertheimer (1923) described the main principles of perceptual
44 grouping that determine what regions of an image constitute perceptual units or objects
45 (Brooks, 2015), such as proximity, similarity, common fate, symmetry, parallelism,
46 closure or good continuation. From the proposal of Palmer (1992, 1999), these classic
47 Gestalt laws are classified as *intrinsic* grouping cues since they are based on built-in
48 properties of the discrete elements (e.g., their shape, position), and a new set of *extrinsic*
49 grouping principles was added based on relations between the discrete elements and
50 other external elements that induce them to group. For example, grouping by common
51 region (Palmer, 1992) refers to the fact that elements located within the same
52 bounded region tend to be grouped together. Also, grouping by connectedness is the
53 tendency of elements that are connected by other elements to be seen as part of the same
54 group (Palmer & Rock, 1994). Prior evidence indicates that these principles can
55 compete effectively against some of the classic Gestalt principles (Brooks, 2015).
56 Remarkably, the ecological rationale behind connectedness arises from the fact that
57 several parts of an object are frequently connected to one another besides showing a
58 visual disparity in color or form (Brooks, 2015). Common region also seems to have an
59 ecological basis arising from hierarchically embedded parts (e.g., leopard's spots or
60 features of a face; Palmer, 1992). Indeed, effects of these grouping cues on object
61 perception and behavior have been reported. For instance, common region can be
62 particularly effective at communicating complex informational structures in realistic
63 environments (Bae & Watson, 2014). Also, element connectedness can affect object
64 perception in patients with neurological lesions altering visual processing (Gilleber &

65 Humphreys, 2015). Furthermore, the relevance of the extrinsic cues for behavior have
66 been persuasively showed by several studies reporting that very young infants (3- to 4-
67 month-olds) are sensitive to the connectedness and common region principles (Quinn &
68 Bhatt, 2015).

69 A well-known limitation of the grouping principles is that they are under *ceteris*
70 *paribus* rules, so that they can predict the configuration perceived only while “other
71 things remain equal” (Palmer, 1999). This restriction makes it difficult to predict the
72 combined effects of multiple conflicting factors applied to the same display. In an
73 attempt to solve this deficiency, several studies have examined the integration of
74 multiple *intrinsic* Gestalt principles when they are combined (e.g., proximity, similarity,
75 collinearity, etc). The main findings on this issue are compatible with additive effects of
76 grouping factors and support the independence of the respective *intrinsic* cues (see
77 Kubovy & van den Berg, 2008 or Peterson & Kimchi, 2015, for a review). The
78 combined grouping effect of *extrinsic* cues have only recently been considered in three
79 studies (Luna and Montoro, 2011; Montoro and Luna, 2015a,b) that examined
80 cooperation and competition between intrinsic principles of proximity and similarity
81 and the extrinsic principle of common region by means of a phenomenological method
82 to quantify spontaneous grouping (Quinlan and Wilton,1998). The results of these
83 studies showed that conflicting cues made grouping weaker and unstable, while
84 cooperating cues made grouping stronger and steady, in line with an additive model for
85 the combination of grouping factors, as proposed by Kubovy and van den Berg (2008).

86 An important theoretical problem concerns the dominance of extrinsic grouping
87 principles when they operate simultaneously in the same display and compete. Findings
88 on this issue might have also some practical consequences such as their potential
89 application for designers to communicate complex informational structure (Bae &

90 Watson, 2014). Thus, a crucial issue in the study of perceptual grouping is the
91 identification of the rules or conditions that govern which principle is dominant when
92 two (or more) principles compete (Peterson & Kimchi, 2015). In this line, Luna and
93 collaborators (2016) examined competition between intrinsic and extrinsic grouping
94 cues by inducing their participants to perceive the displays grouped in a determined way
95 before responding which allowed the measurement of the accuracy and the speed of
96 responses. This scheme provided measures of perceptual grouping dominance similar to
97 those collected in research concerning dominance processing in hierarchical stimuli
98 (Navon, 1977). In Luna et al.'s Experiment 2, a dominance of the common region cue
99 over connectedness was indicated by (i) an advantage effect of common region (faster
100 responses to groups formed by common region than to those formed by connectedness)
101 and (ii) a bidirectional but asymmetrical interference due to the fact that grouping by
102 connectedness was slowed by the presence of the competing common region cue more
103 than vice versa. Similarly, a dominance of common region over shape similarity was
104 found in Experiment 3. Notably, in both experiments, the strength of the grouping cues
105 was previously equated with phenomenological reports.

106 Crucially, the use of tasks using selective attention to groups to study extrinsic
107 grouping factors could be particularly threatened by the intrusion of alternative
108 strategies of performing the task, which are non-related to the perceptual grouping
109 operations (Palmer & Beck, 2007). In this sense, it seems possible that some
110 participants attend to the inductors (i.e. contours defining a region or lines connecting
111 items) to achieve task requirements while ignoring the discrete elements to be grouped.
112 For instance, in Luna et al. (2016), some participants might have responded by
113 considering only the location of the extrinsic inductors on either the right or the left.

114 Given the importance of identifying the conditions that determine which of two
115 competing extrinsic principles will dominate the perceived organization, in the present
116 work we further examined the competition between common region and element
117 connectedness principles overcoming prior limitations. In addition, an important issue
118 was to explore the dominance dynamics of extrinsic grouping cues in tasks which did
119 not require selective attention to the grouping cues in order to examine whether the
120 pattern of results is similar to that found using approaches demanding attention to
121 grouping (Luna et al., 2016).

122 To investigate the competition between common region and connectedness, we
123 used the *repetition discrimination task* (RDT; Palmer & Beck, 2007), an indirect task
124 that does not require explicit attention to grouping cues. This task also allowed to
125 examine and prevent strategic effects that might be found in selective attentions tasks
126 (Palmer & Beck, 2007). This task provides an unbiased measure of the dominance
127 dynamics of extrinsic grouping based on reactions times (RTs) and accuracy. In
128 particular, the participants had to discriminate the repeated shape (square or circle) in a
129 row of nine alternating elements. The grouping factors could influence the perceived
130 organization of squares and circles by facilitating or hindering the task. Thus, RT
131 differences between experimental conditions could be taken as an indirect measure of
132 grouping effects. Remarkably, the RDT has been successfully employed to provide
133 indirect evidence for both common region and connectedness single cues (Palmer &
134 Beck, 2007, Experiment 3). However, to our knowledge, the RDT has never been used
135 to study the competition of two different grouping factors acting in the same display. A
136 critical factor to consider when combining two grouping cues is their grouping strength,
137 that is, the subjective saliency of the respective grouping factors (Schmidt & Schmidt,
138 2013). Thus, we first conducted a scaling task to select the appropriate stimuli in order

139 to ensure that the grouping strength of both cues was equated, as recommended in
140 Kubovy and van den Berg (2008). Since prior studies observed between-subjects
141 divergences in phenomenological measures of grouping (e.g., Schmidt & Schmidt,
142 2013; Montoro & Luna, 2015a,b), we obtained individual ratings of grouping strength
143 for every participant from the scaling task. This allowed us to personalize the stimulus
144 set displayed in the subsequent RDT. In the scaling task, participants had to equate the
145 grouping strength of both principles by adjusting the thickness of the connectors acting
146 as connectedness cues while the physical features of the common region inductor
147 remained unaltered. We chose a simple one-dimension scaling task to make it more
148 intuitive to participants.

149

150 **Method**

151 Participants

152 Twelve undergraduate students (five men; age range: 19-46 years, $M = 27.3$, $SD = 8.6$)
153 from the UNED participated in the experiment and received course credits for their
154 participation. All of them had normal or corrected-to-normal vision. The experimental
155 procedure was approved by the Local Ethics Committee and conforms to the
156 Declaration of Helsinki.

157 Apparatus

158 The stimuli were displayed on a 19-inch LCD-LED color monitor with a 75-Hz refresh
159 rate, a 5:4 aspect ratio, and a resolution of 1280 x 1024 pixels, controlled by a personal
160 computer running E-Prime 2.0 software (Psychology Software Tools, 1996-2013).
161 Viewing distance was approximately 60 cm. Responses were recorded via a standard
162 keyboard.

163 Stimuli

164 The stimulus set was based on Palmer and Beck's (2007) displays. The basic display
165 consists of a row of nine dark (RGB: 0; 0.06 cd/m²) equidistant elements that alternate
166 between squares and circles, which subtended 9 × 9 mm (0.86° v.a.). The entire array of
167 nine elements measured 152 mm (14.22° v.a.) vertically. The edge-to-edge distance
168 between elements was 9 mm (0.86° v.a.).

169 For the RDT, forty-eight different stimuli were drawn (see Figure 1b), twenty-four for
170 the single conditions and twenty-four displays for the competing conditions. The nine
171 elements alternated between squares and circles, except for a single pair of adjacent
172 similar shapes somewhere within the middle seven elements. In the common region
173 only condition, four light grey (RGB: 128; 14.1 cd/m²) oval outlines (33 × 21 mm; 3.15°
174 × 2.01° v.a.) and a semi-oval were added to the pattern as common region cues. In the
175 connectedness only condition, five light grey (RGB: 128; 14.1 cd/m²) connectors
176 (vertical length: 9 mm; 0.86° v.a.) were added as connectedness cues. The thickness
177 value of the connectors was personalized for each participant based on the results of the
178 scaling task (see *Results* section). In the competing conditions, both ovals and
179 connectors were included as part of the stimuli.

180 In the scaling task, all the stimuli were competing patterns alternating square/circle
181 shapes with absent target pairs (i.e. without a repeated pair of elements; see Figure 1a).
182 Thirty different stimuli were created by manipulating the thickness value of the
183 connectors from 1 to 30 pixels by one-unit increments (pixels: 1, 2, ..., 29, 30).

184 -----
185 Insert Figure 1 about here
186 -----

187 Design and procedure

188 The 2×2 design included two within-subjects factors: Stimulus type (single or
189 competing grouping cues) and Grouping cue joining the target pair (common region vs.
190 connectedness). These four different types of stimuli were combined with six different
191 positions of the target pair (elements 2-3, 3-4, 4-5, 5-6, 6-7, 7-8, counting from the left),
192 two shapes of the target pair (squares vs. circles) and two repetitions to obtain 96 trials
193 in each experimental block. RTs and error rates were measured.

194 Participants were tested individually in a dimly lit room in two different sessions, one
195 for the scaling task, and another one for the RDT. In the scaling task participants had to
196 adjust the thickness of the connectors joining elements until their grouping strength
197 appeared as equally strong as the grouping strength of the common region cue, so that
198 the visual grouping of the elements in pairs were equally salient in figures joined
199 together by connectors and in figures included in ovals. In order to avoid confounds, the
200 instructions emphasized that judgments must be based on the grouping strength or
201 subjective salience of the extrinsic cues, which does not necessarily imply that the
202 inductors (connectors and ovals) had to be equated in physical thickness. Each
203 participant completed one practice trial and six scaling trials: three trials starting with 1
204 pixel in thickness and other three beginning with 30 pixels in thickness. The order of
205 presentation of the increasing and decreasing trials was alternated between subjects.

206 Participants increased or decreased the thickness of the connectors by pressing the right
207 or the left arrow keys of the keyboard with the index fingers of both hands. After verbal
208 confirmation of their decision the specific thickness value was recorded without
209 informing the participant. There was no time limit. A mean pixels value collapsing the
210 six judgments was computed for each participant, which was implemented as the
211 thickness value of the connectors in the stimuli included in the subsequent RDT.

212 In the RDT, participants responded as quickly as possible while avoiding errors by
213 pressing one of two keys (i.e. “Z” and “M”) with their left or right index to indicate the
214 shape (circle or square) of the repeated pair of elements. Key assignment was
215 counterbalanced across participants. The stimulus array was presented on the centre of
216 the screen and remained until response. The inter-trial interval was 800 ms. There were
217 a practice block with 48 trials and six experimental blocks consisting of 96 trials each,
218 for a total of 576 experimental trials. Feedback was provided only for the practice trials.

219

220 **Results**

221 Scaling task

222 Figure 2a shows the results for each participant. The range of mean pixels adjusted
223 values fluctuated between 7 and 18 (mean = 12; SD = 4.1), showing a remarkable
224 variability among participants in their perception of relative grouping strength, as
225 expected. In contrast, the rather small standard errors (see Figure 2a) suggest that
226 participants were very consistent in their judgments across the trials.

227 Repetition discrimination task

228 Median RTs of correct responses and mean accuracy rates were submitted to separate
229 analyses of variance (ANOVAs) with Stimulus type and Grouping cue joining the target
230 as within-subjects factors.

231 *RT analysis.* Inaccurate responses (103 of 6,912; 1.5% of trials) and RTs greater than
232 4000 or less than 200 ms (11 of 6,809; 0.16 of trials) were excluded from the RT
233 analysis. Analyses on RTs showed a significant main effect of Stimulus Type, $F(1, 11)$
234 $= 162.9$, $MSe = 6136$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .94$, indicating that RTs for single trials (721 ms)
235 were shorter than those for competing ones (1010 ms). The main effect of Grouping cue
236 was also significant, $F(1, 11) = 126.8$, $MSe = 8276.1$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .92$, showing that

237 targets included in common region (717 ms) were responded faster than targets joined
238 by connectors (1013 ms). Finally, the interaction between the two factors was
239 significant $F(2, 30) = 87.41$, $MSe = 8709$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .89$, indicating that the
240 interference effect of common region on the discrimination of targets grouped by
241 connectedness (the difference between single and competing stimuli) was much greater
242 ($\Delta 540$ ms: 1283 ms – 743 ms) than the interference of connectedness on the
243 discrimination of targets grouped by common region ($\Delta 37$ ms: 736 ms – 699 ms). Pair-
244 wise comparisons applying the Bonferroni correction showed significant differences
245 between all pairs from the experimental conditions (all $ps \leq .01$).
246 Additionally, correlation analyses between the mean thickness value (pixels) of the
247 connectors from the scaling task and the median RTs in the three conditions that
248 displayed connectedness cues were conducted. None of the correlations reached
249 significance (all $p > .10$), supporting the independence between subjective grouping
250 strength and the responses in the RDT.

251 *Accuracy analysis.* Hit rates oscillated between 96% and 100%. The results of the
252 ANOVAs showed no significant main or interactive effects.

253 -----
254 Insert Figure 2 about here
255 -----

256 **Discussion**

257 In this study we explored the integration of two competing extrinsic grouping
258 cues by means of an indirect task without explicit attention to the grouping factors,
259 which prevents strategic effects or biases unrelated to grouping operations. The results
260 clearly supported that grouping by common region dominates the perceived
261 organization of the display when the grouping factors were not explicitly attended. For

262 the competing stimuli, the responses were considerably faster when the target elements
263 were within the same oval compared to those observed in displays in which they
264 remained in different ovals. The single conditions also showed faster responses for
265 targets grouped by common region than for targets grouped by connectedness. Notably,
266 RT differences between single cue conditions ($\Delta 37$ ms) were clearly smaller than those
267 found between the competitive conditions ($\Delta 540$ ms). Thus, even though both results
268 reflect the dominance of common region over connectedness, it seems unlikely to
269 attribute the rather large difference between competition conditions only to the
270 existence of the small processing advantage found in the single conditions.

271 Additionally, an influence of connectedness in conflicting conditions was observed
272 since RTs to target pairs linked by a connector in different ovals were significantly
273 slower than in the common region single condition ($\Delta 7$ ms).

274 The relative dominance of common region over other grouping factors
275 corroborated previous data obtained with direct measures based on phenomenological
276 reports or choice-reaction time tasks. In Luna and Montoro (2011), the common region
277 cue was rated by observers as being stronger than proximity in a competing condition,
278 even though both factors were judged as comparable in their respective single
279 conditions (but see Montoro and Luna, 2015b). Also, Montoro et al. (2015) observed
280 faster responses to common region than to luminance similarity in a direct choice-RT
281 task that did not include a competing condition. Similarly, using a task which required
282 selective attention to the grouping cues, Luna et al. (2016) reported a dominance of
283 common region over shape similarity and connectedness when they compete in the
284 same display despite being equal in phenomenological grouping strength. Remarkably,
285 the present results provide evidence for the first time of dominance for common region
286 cues when they compete with connectedness in an indirect task that does not require

287 explicit attention to grouping cues and avoids the use of some strategic biases. From an
288 applied perspective, Bae and Watson (2014) observed that common region was the most
289 accurate, fastest and most preferred structural communication in comparison to
290 proximity, color similarity, connectedness and good continuation. Consequently, the
291 authors recommended designers to use common region in real contexts to communicate
292 complex informational configurations. Our results could have some implications for the
293 communicative applications of visualization by providing some cues that improve the
294 organization of information in charts, matrices or lists. Furthermore, the indirect effects
295 of extrinsic grouping cues might be useful for improving object perception in patients
296 with visual system damage (Gilleber & Humphreys, 2015).

297 Interestingly, the unequivocal processing dominance of common region in our
298 study occurred even though the phenomenological grouping strength of the grouping
299 cues was equated for each participant. The absence of correlation between the data from
300 the scaling task and the performance in the RDT reinforces the dissociation between
301 both measures. Remarkably, the inspection of individual data revealed a processing
302 advantage for common region in the competing conditions even for the only participant
303 who showed faster RTs to connectedness compared to common region in the single
304 grouped conditions (see supplementary materials: section b): [http://](http://www.ucace.com/app/download/27209144/Montoro+et+al._PBR.pdf)
305 http://www.ucace.com/app/download/27209144/Montoro+et+al._PBR.pdf). Finally, the
306 finding of similar RT differences in both competing and single conditions in a
307 preliminary study with an scaling tasks in which common region was conveyed by
308 luminance provides further evidence for the consistency of our dat (see supplementary
309 materials: section a): [http://](http://www.ucace.com/app/download/27209144/Montoro+et+al._PBR.pdf)
310 http://www.ucace.com/app/download/27209144/Montoro+et+al._PBR.pdf). In fact, these
311 results were not completely unexpected since similar discrepancies between direct and

312 indirect measures of grouping have been repeatedly observed in previous studies
313 (Schmidt and Schmidt 2013; Luna et al., 2016; Montoro et al., 2015b; Palmer and Beck,
314 2007). This dissociation has been attributed to the fact that the perceptual parameters of
315 grouping are not necessarily represented in an equivalent manner by the
316 phenomenological perception and by the visuo-motor system. Consequently, equating
317 two stimuli with a subjective method does not guarantee a parallel effect in the visuo-
318 motor system. This finding is especially relevant because it uncover the dissociated
319 cognitive mechanisms involved in perceptual grouping tasks and, additionally, leads
320 directly to an important new question, which should be addressed in future research,
321 that is: will visual parameters generating identical behavioral effects be perceived as
322 similar by phenomenological experience? (see Schmidt & Schmidt, 2013, for a similar
323 account).

324 As other authors have discussed none of the measures should be privileged a
325 priori to the detriment of the other because they both have strengths and weaknesses and
326 they are convergent measures of grouping (Kubovy & Gepshtein, 2003; Palmer & Beck,
327 2007). In phenomenological methods, a direct measure of grouping is achieved based
328 on participant reports of the grouping strength they perceive in each trial, so a more
329 cognitive than perceptual evaluation strategy might be adopted. In contrast, the removal
330 of spontaneous grouping in indirect tasks leaves open the possibility of not being able to
331 measure purely grouping (Kubovy & Gepshtein, 2003; Palmer & Beck, 2007). Notably,
332 as in the current study, it seems crucial to avoid the adoption of alternative strategies
333 non-related to grouping operations when exploring extrinsic grouping. Nonetheless, a
334 complete characterization of the dominance dynamics of grouping needs convergent
335 evidence with different types of measures.

336 **Author note**

337 This work was supported by the *Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad* (MINECO)
338 of Spain (PSI2015-68368-P (MINECO/FEDER)) and the *Comunidad de Madrid*
339 (H2015/HUM-3327). The authors acknowledge two reviewers for their insightful
340 comments on a previous version of the manuscript.

341

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399 **Figure captions**

400 **Figure 1.** Examples of some stimuli displayed in the scaling task and in the RDT. The
401 thickness of the connectors in the right panel is equal to 15 pixels.

402 **Figure 2.** (a) Mean adjusted thickness values for each participant in the scaling task. (b)
403 Mean reaction times (ms) and standard error bars for the experimental conditions of the
404 RDT.

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424 Figure 1

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444 Figure 2

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